

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES IN DAIRY INDUSTRY MANUFACTURING

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ABSTRACT

The dairy industry is constantly evolving to meet rising consumer demands and enhance production efficiency. This review explores cutting-edge mechanisms and technologies that have revolutionized dairy product manufacturing. It focuses on advancements in automation, fermentation techniques, packaging innovations, and sustainability practices. The adoption of these technologies not only improves product quality but also tackles key challenges such as waste management and resource optimization.

Keywords: Dairy industry, Technology, Innovation, Packaging, Advance process

